

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

ABCE1 functions in multi-drug resistance in human cancer in metastasis to the bone.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe here a function for the ATP-binding cassette gene *ABCE1* in multi-drug resistance in human cancer (1-3), supported by evidence by demonstrating its transcriptional up-regulation with significance at the transcriptome level in metastasis to distant organ sites in human breast cancer (4, 5), and by separate evidence demonstrating that ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance: in resistance to a platinum agent, in resistance to doxorubicin, and in resistance to paclitaxel (2).

Results

Figure 1: ABCE1 is differentially expressed in the bone metastases of humans with breast cancer.

I. Metastasis to the bone in humans with breast cancer.

n=3 MCF7 (human; breast cancer)

n=3 MCF7b bone metastatic variant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6059	9.06E-19	0.0629	-8.846185	-0.5561594	3225.94	ABCE1	1788/20047	91.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in human breast cancer cells (MCF7) and a metastatic MCF7 variant, MCF7b, we discovered differential expression of ATP binding cassette subfamily E member 1, encoded by *ABCE1* in metastasis to the bone in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *ABCE1* changed more than 90% of the human breast cancer transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 20,047 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *ABCE1* messenger RNA in breast cancer bone metastasis, demonstrating up-regulation of *ABCE1* during disease progression and metastasis.

Discussion

We described here transcriptional induction of a gene with functions in multi-drug resistance, in bone metastasis in human breast cancer. Novel approaches to challenging metastasis and resistance will utilize chemotherapy in conjunction with i) kinase and phosphatase inhibitors targeted to tissue and tumor type whose functions overlap with that of growth factor and growth factor receptor inhibitors, ii) inhibitors of the ATP-binding cassette family (multi-drug resistance pumps), and iii) CDK4/6 inhibitors, which function as senescence-inducing agents.

1 **References**

2 1. Gottesman, M.M., Fojo, T. and Bates, S.E., 2002. Multidrug resistance in cancer: role of
3 ATP-dependent transporters. *Nature reviews cancer*, 2(1), pp.48-58.

4 2. Mamoor, S. 2025. ATP-binding cassette genes function in multi-drug resistance in human cancer.

5 3. Robey, R.W., Pluchino, K.M., Hall, M.D., Fojo, A.T., Bates, S.E. and Gottesman, M.M., 2018.
6 Revisiting the role of ABC transporters in multidrug-resistant cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 18(7),
pp.452-464.

7 4. GSE121677: Clements, M.E. and Johnson, R.W., 2020. PREX1 drives spontaneous bone
8 dissemination of ER+ breast cancer cells. *Oncogene*, 39(6), pp.1318-1334.

9 5. GSE55715: Johnson, J., Bessette, D.C., Saunus, J.M., Smart, C.E., Song, S., Johnston, R.L.,
10 Cocciardi, S., Rozali, E.N., Johnstone, C.N., Vargas, A.C. and Kazakoff, S.H., 2018. Characterization of a
11 novel breast cancer cell line derived from a metastatic bone lesion of a breast cancer patient. *Breast
12 Cancer Research and Treatment*, 170, pp.179-188.

13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We measured total transcription in primary tumors and metastasis to distant organ sites including the bones, the brain, the liver and the lungs using microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets (GSEXXXXX and GSEXXXXX) and R-based computational software for exact quantitative determination of multi-drug resistant pump transcriptional induction at the transcriptome level.